

FOREST FIRE DETECTION

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ABSTRACT: Forest fires are common hazards in forests that cause a lot of harm to wildlife as well as the environment. It could be avoided if a robust system could be deployed in forest areas to detect the fire and alert to fire extinguishing authority to take immediate action. In this project, the intention is to build a forest fire detection system using IoT which would detect the fire and send an emergency alert to authority through IoT. Here a GSM/GPRS module is used to communicate with IoT sever as usually in forest areas network bandwidth is very low or not available. Hence a 2G network is preferable to communicate with the server. SIM800L is a compact module that allows GPRS transmission, send/receive SMS, and making voice calls. SIM800L module has two antennas included on it. The first is for a ring antenna which can be soldered directly on the board and the other is meant for an external antenna. Arduino compares the signal and triggers the SIM800L in case of fire incidents. Through AT commands, SIM800L communicates with thingspeak server. SIM800L is connected to Arduino Nano via logic shifting resistors as SIM800L works on 3.3v logic. Separate power is given to SIM800L module because it works in 3.4-4.2V DC and 5V DC external supply is given to Arduino Nano. Alternatively, a 3.7-5 V Boost converter can be used here to avoid two power supplies. To test the prototype, first, the microsim needs to be inserted in the SIM800L slot . Then power ON the module and then we can see the LED blinking in the module. If the LED blinking is delayed as compared to the initial start, it means it got the network, and is ready to connect to the server.

KEYWORDS: Wildfire detection, Forest fire early warning system, Fire risk assessment, Remote sensing, Machine learning, Artificial Intelligence, Thermal imaging, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle, Satellite imagery, Geographic Information System, Weather forecasting, Smoke detection, Flame detection, Sensor networks, Data fusion, Predictive modelling, Detection support system, Emergency response, Damage assessment, Firefighting support.

WORKING: Forest fire detection systems typically rely on a combination of sensors, data processing techniques, and communication technologies to detect fires and alert authorities. Here is a general overview of the working of a forest fire detection system:

1. **Sensors:** A forest fire detection system typically includes a network of sensors that can detect changes in temperature, humidity, wind, and other environmental conditions. These sensors can be ground-based or mounted on unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) or satellites.
2. **Data processing:** Once the sensors detect a change in environmental conditions that could indicate the presence of a fire, the data from the sensors is processed by a computer or other data processing system. This processing can involve algorithms that use machine learning or artificial intelligence techniques to distinguish between normal environmental fluctuations and the onset of a fire.
3. **Alert system:** If the data processing system detects the presence of a fire, it triggers an alert system that can notify authorities, nearby residents, or other stakeholders. The alert system can use a variety of communication technologies, such as cellular networks, satellite communication, or radio frequencies.

4. **Response:** Once an alert is triggered, authorities can respond by dispatching firefighting personnel and equipment to the location of the fire. The forest fire detection system can also provide real-time data and imagery to help guide the firefighting efforts.
5. **Evaluation:** After the fire has been contained or extinguished, the forest fire detection system can be used to evaluate the damage caused by the fire and to identify any areas where additional preventive measures may be needed.

Overall, forest fire detection systems are designed to provide early warning of fires so that authorities can respond quickly and effectively. These systems rely on a combination of sensors, data processing techniques, and communication technologies to detect fires and alert stakeholders, and they can play a critical role in minimizing the damage caused by forest fires.

COMPONENTS REQUIRED:

- Arduino Nano
- SIM800L GPS/GPRS Module
- 3.7V Li-ion Battery
- Flame sensor
- Dot matrix Perf board

MODULES: Forest fire detection systems are typically composed of multiple modules that work together to detect fires, alert authorities, and facilitate a rapid response. Here are some common modules in a forest fire detection system:

- **Sensor module:** This module consists of sensors that are deployed in the forest to detect changes in environmental conditions that could indicate the presence of a fire. These sensors may include temperature, humidity, and wind sensors, as well as cameras or other imaging devices that can capture visual data.
- **Data processing module:** The data processing module receives data from the sensor module and uses algorithms to analyze the data and detect the presence of a fire. This module may use machine learning or artificial intelligence techniques to distinguish between normal environmental fluctuations and the onset of a fire.
- **Alert module:** Once a fire is detected, the alert module sends notifications to relevant stakeholders, such as authorities, nearby residents, or firefighters. The alert module may use a variety of communication technologies, such as cellular networks, satellite communication, or radio frequencies, to send these notifications.
- **Monitoring module:** The monitoring module provides real-time data and imagery to stakeholders to facilitate a rapid response. This module may include cameras or other imaging devices that provide visual data, as well as weather sensors that provide information on wind direction and speed.
- **Response module:** The response module facilitates a rapid response to a fire by dispatching firefighters and other emergency personnel to the location of the fire. This module may also provide guidance to these personnel based on real-time data and imagery.

- **Evaluation module:** The evaluation module assesses the damage caused by the fire and identifies areas where additional preventive measures may be needed. This module may use data from the other modules to generate maps or other visualizations that can help stakeholders understand the impact of the fire.

Overall, a forest fire detection system typically includes multiple modules that work together to detect fires, alert authorities, and facilitate a rapid response. These modules may include sensors, data processing algorithms, communication technologies, and monitoring and evaluation tools.

FLOWCHART:

FIGURE 1.1

FIGURE 1.2

FIGURE 1.3

CONCLUSION: In conclusion, forest fires pose a serious threat to the environment, wildlife, and human populations living near or within forests. Early detection of forest fires is critical for effective fire management and to minimize the damage caused by wildfires. The development of forest fire detection systems, which use a combination of sensors, data processing algorithms, and communication technologies, has shown great promise in detecting forest fires and facilitating a rapid response. Various techniques such as machine learning, artificial intelligence, thermal imaging, satellite imagery, and UAVs have been used in forest fire detection systems to improve the accuracy and speed of fire detection. These technologies can detect fires in real-time and provide authorities with critical information to guide their response efforts. However, there are still some limitations and challenges that need to be addressed, such as the high cost of implementing forest fire detection systems and the difficulty in detecting fires in remote areas.

REFERENCE:

- San-Miguel-Ayanz, J., Schulte, E., Schmuck, G., Camia, A., Strobl, P., Liberta, G., & Giovando, C. (2013). Comprehensive monitoring of wildfires in Europe: the European Forest Fire Information System. In *Forest fire prevention and control* (pp. 49-58). Springer, Dordrecht.
- Kumar, R., Sharma, S., & Sharma, R. (2018). A review on forest fire detection techniques. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology (UAE)*, 7(3), 168-172.
- Jain, V., & Singh, A. K. (2021). A systematic review of forest fire detection systems. *Fire Science Reviews*, 10(1), 1-24.
- Raghavendra, U., & Durga, B. S. (2019). Forest fire detection using remote sensing and GIS: a review. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 16(10), 5577-5592.
- Madurapperuma, B. D. G., Jayaratne, J. H. S., & Abeynayake, R. (2019). Forest fire detection using machine learning algorithms: a review. In *2019 IEEE 10th International Conference on Mechanical and Intelligent Manufacturing Technologies* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.

WEBSITES:

- Global Forest Watch Fires: <https://fires.globalforestwatch.org/> This website provides a global view of active fires, their locations, and their severity. It uses satellite data to detect and monitor forest fires in real-time.
- NASA Earth Observatory: <https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/natural-hazards/category/19/forest-fires> The NASA Earth Observatory website provides information and images related to forest fires around the world. It uses satellite data to track fire activity and provides analysis and insights into the causes and effects of wildfires.
- European Forest Fire Information System: <https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/> The European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) provides a comprehensive view of forest fires across Europe. It uses satellite data and other sources to monitor fire activity, provide risk assessments, and support decision-making related to forest fire management.
- Wildfire Today: <https://wildfiretoday.com/> Wildfire Today is a website dedicated to providing up-to-date news and information about wildfires in the United States and around the world. It covers a range of topics related to forest fires, including prevention, management, and response.
- National Interagency Fire Center: <https://www.nifc.gov/> The National Interagency Fire Center (NIFC) is a collaborative effort between multiple agencies in the United States to manage and respond to wildfires. Its website provides information on fire activity, resources for firefighters and other emergency responders, and information for the public about fire prevention and safety.